

**Ancestors, Metaphysics of Sexuality and Colonial Politics of Sexual
Waithood in Africa**

Artwell Nhemachena,¹ & Munyaradzi Mawere.²

*¹Professor of Anthropology and Sociology,
University of Namibia, & Research Fellow, University of
South Africa. Corresponding author.*

Email: artwellnhemachena@ymail.com

*²Professor of African Studies,
Great Zimbabwe University, & Professor Extraordinaire, University of South Africa.*

Abstract:

Arguing that colonialists disrupted African metaphysics to render them vulnerable to colonial and imperial [sexual] exploitation, this paper contends that ancestors provided metaphysical protective shields to descendants. Drawing on Shona (a people of Zimbabwe) proverb *ziva kwawakabva, mudzimu weshiri uri mudendere* (know your origins, the ancestral spirit of the bird is in its nest), it contends that colonialists condemned African ancestors to dissuade Africans from seeking guidance and protection from them. Instead of remembering their origins in the ancestral world, with sexual morality and normativity, Africans were taught by colonialists that their human origins were in animals from which, colonialists argued, Africans evolved. Consequently, instead of craving to [sexually] take after human ancestors, some Africans crave to [sexually] take after animals portrayed as the origins of humans. Sadly, some contemporary Eurocentric scholars writing on animism continue to deny separations between nonhumans and indigenous humans, including in matters of sexuality. This paper examines vulnerabilities suffered by Africans who got disoriented from their cultural normativity and lost ancestral metaphysical protection in the realm of sexuality.

Keywords: Ancestors, Sexuality, Africa, Colonial, Worlds, Metaphysics.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution
International License (CC BY 4.0).

1. INTRODUCTION

Colonial treatments of Africans as having originated from nonhuman animals unleash animal sexualities contrary to the inhibitions of humanistic ancestral sexual moralities, etiquette and ethics. Whereas, in African metaphysics, descendants were named after their ancestors after whom they took in terms of what the Shona (people of Zimbabwe) call *nhodzera*, colonialists not only disrupted ancestral metaphysics but they also simianized Africans in the sense of treating them as indistinct from nonhuman animals without sexual morality, etiquette and ethics (Smith & Manaitiu, 2016; Hund, Mills & Sebastiani, 2016; Holmes, 2016; Engmann, 2012). Defining metaphysics of sexuality in terms of entanglements between African ancestral spirits and the sexuality of their descendants, this paper also argues that colonialists created colonial politics of sexual waithood by disrupting African ancestral metaphysics of *chronos* and *kairos* in respect of times for marriages. Put differently, instead of being regulated in terms of ancestral mores, etiquette, ethics and time, colonial animalistic sexualities depended on animalistic instincts that generated vulnerabilities to colonial sexual exploitation, including in the colonial sex industry. The ways in which colonialists disrupted and decentered humanistic ancestral metaphysics of sexuality are underscored by Evola (1983, p. 9) who observes that:

Since its inception, sexology, in monographs having scientific pretensions, has been influenced by the legacy of nineteenth-century materialism, which took as its premises the theories of Darwin and biology...They tell us that man sprang in the beginning from the animal by “natural evolution”, and they have described man’s sexual and erotic life in terms of an extension of animal instincts.

Thus, instead of striving to take after the sexuality of their human ancestors, some Africans have been impelled to strive to take after animalistic sexualities, based on colonial misrepresentations of the animal as the origin of humans. Instead of following the transcendental mores and conventions of ancestral spirits, some Africans were caused to follow the nonconventional, unpredictable and non-rational animal spirits of colonial sexuality. Colonial sexualities disrupt and challenge the conventional and normative because colonialists profit from nonconventional and nonnormative sexuality. In African metaphysics, ancestors are understood to be different from nonhuman animals, they are understood to be rational beings in the form of human spirits, and not animal spirits. By depicting African ancestors as animals, colonialists misrepresented the ancestors as irrational, illogical, immoral, unethical and as animal spirits, and not human spirits. By extension, they presupposed that Africans who consulted the ancestors were also irrational because it is irrational and illogical for a human to consult an animal for advice.

Contrary to colonial misrepresentations, African ancestors are understood to live in the ancestral worlds and not in nonhuman animals, although they may use animals as force-multipliers in the human world. A brief focus on conceptualizations of the ancestral worlds helps to put the argument into perspective.

2. ANCESTRAL WORLDS AND OTHER PARALLEL UNIVERSES: METAPHYSICS OF SEXUAL PURITY

While colonialists historically disconnected Africans from the worlds of African ancestors, they ironically connected African sexuality to nonhuman animals, and to global capital where African sexuality would be exploited for profit. Indeed, while they dismiss the parallel worlds where African ancestors live, Western scientists ironically engage in searches for parallel universes, multiverses and galaxies, and they are looking for intelligent life in other planets to which they want to connect (Lim, 2023 March 22; Tegmark, 2003; Drake, 2023 March 13; Battaglia et al., 2015; Lewis, 2020 June 18; Praet & Salazar, 2017; Nhemachena, 2025). In other words, much as Africans sought to connect to the invisible ancestral worlds, scientists are searching for parallel worlds or the multiverse – they are looking for other universes beyond the observable universe (Drake, 2023 March 13; Kaku, 2005; Tegmark, 2003; Griffith University, 2014 October 30; Mahaswa & Kim, 2023). The scientists believe such parallel universes have intelligent life which is advanced enough to communicate with the human world and, of course, anthropologists are now also participating in the search for intelligent life on other planets (Lewis, 2020 June 18; Salazar, 2018 November 7; Praet & Salazar, 2017; Ball, 2023 August 21; Billings, 2019). Thus, writing about the existence of parallel universes in *Scientific American*, the scientist, Tegmark (2003, p. 3) states that:

In particular, there are infinitely many other inhabited planets, including not just one but infinitely many with people with the same appearance, name and memories as you. Indeed, there are infinitely many other regions the size of our observable universe, where every possible cosmic history is played out.

The point here is that ancestors, that is those who led normative and moral lives in the human world, are understood to shuttle between the ancestral world and the human world to protect their living descendants (Nhemachena, 2025). The African ancestors are understood to act as spiritual guardians, similar to saints, who protect their living descendants in the human world; also, the ancestors are understood to control the sexuality of their descendants and indeed, during marriage ceremonies, ancestors are invoked and they are asked to bless and protect the marriages (Nhemachena, 2017, 2024b; Makaudze, 2015a; Aschwanden, 1982). By protecting their descendants, ancestors ensure that they do not suffer sexual vulnerability and that they sexually behave in terms of the ancestral humanistic mores, ethics, etiquette, norms and conventions. This is why

matters of sexuality, marriages and families involved many rituals and ceremonies designed to connect Africans to the protective ancestral worlds and to ancestors as guardians of sexuality.

The problem is that even anthropologists, who claimed anthropological holism, could not make any trips to the African ancestral worlds to have a holistic view of African sexuality. Because they could neither make trips to, nor sense the African ancestral worlds, colonial anthropologists depicted African sexuality as animalistic in origin, as bestial, beastly, lascivious, promiscuous, permissive and unrestrained (Holmes, 2016; Engmann, 2012; Nhemachena, 2024a). Much as African ancestors are guardians of the land (Schoffeleers, 2000), they are also understood to be guardians of the sexuality of their descendants which they protect through, for instance, inducing guiding dreams and through emitting guiding ancestral voices that are still heard by some Africans who still follow African religion and spirituality. Indeed, even European philosophers like Socrates, Plato and Rene Descartes heard guiding voices and dreams which they understood as their spiritual guardians (Nhemachena, 2020; Graham, 2016; Kenny, 2003; Dvorak, 2019). Socrates for example heard the voice when he was about to do something wrong and when he was on the right track the voice would remain quiet.

Africans conceive of the human world, which is inhabited by living humans, but they also conceive of the transcendental ancestral worlds, addressed as *Nyikadzimu* among the Shona people (Mararike, 1999; Nhemachena, 2017, 2025; Kroesbergen, 2020; Kgatle, 2024; Onongha, 2023). There is also the world in which God (variously addressed in African languages) is understood to reside (Nhemachena, 2017, 2025; Garbett, 1998; Gelfand, 1959). Besides these worlds, there is also the world of witches which is populated by witches and their nonhuman intelligent familiars (Nhemachena, 2025). In African cosmologies, God and ancestors work together - with ancestors acting as intermediaries between humans and God. While the world of ancestors and the world in which God resides are interested in keeping cultural morals, normativity, uprightness, etiquette, ethics, humanness, good behavior, peace and harmony, the world of witches and their intelligent nonhuman familiars does the opposite. The world of witches and their intelligent nonhuman familiars strive to upend cultural morals, cultural normativity, ethics, etiquette, good manners, peace, humanness, harmony and normativity (Nhemachena, 2024, 2025). In this regard, African metaphysics, including metaphysics of sexuality, is interworldly in the sense that it explains sexuality in terms of the existence of parallel but partially connected worlds.

Ignoring the African metaphysics of sexuality, colonialists reductively explained sexuality in terms of social constructivism, and they reductively explained sexual morality in terms of European Victorian traditions while derisively explaining African sexuality in terms of the supposed animal origins of humans. Put differently, colonial scholarship traces origins of human sexuality to animalism rather than to the ancestral and Godly realms which constitute the origins of humanity in African metaphysics. The consequence is that the original ancestral morality, ethics, etiquette and sexual normativity have been cancelled out. After cancelling out the original ancestors and God as the origins of humanity, colonial scholarship then proceeded to claim that morality, ethics, etiquette and sexual normativity originated from Western Victorian traditions of purity, chastity and normativity (Nhemachena, 2024a). Colonialists sought to denigrate and degrade Africans by depicting and treating them as subhumans, irrational, animalistic, immoral, beastly, promiscuous, lascivious and so on. Thus, it was convenient for colonialists to

depict Africans, including African sexuality, as originating from the supposed animal ancestors, in the Darwinist sense.

Having reduced human sexuality to animal origins, colonial scholars proceeded to define human sexual freedom in terms of animal-like freedom to enjoy sex without regard to cultural norms, normativity, values, morality and purity – and it is such a kind of [animal] freedom which they then defined as decolonization of sexuality. For some Eurocentric scholars, decolonization of human sexuality involves the freedom to engage in animal-like sex as well as to engage in sex with animals (Picq, 2019; Burns, 2020; Currier, 2012; Nhemachena, 2024a). Whereas scholars like Douglas (1966) have detailed how purity, including sexual purity, is important to avoid getting into danger and pollution, the colonial reduction of human sexuality to animal origins is witnessing the growth of prostitution, incest, bestiality, homosexuality and other forms of sexualities that disregard cultural sexual normativity (Nhemachena, 2024c; Nhemachena & Warikandwa, 2019).

Such subversive sexualities are gaining traction in Zimbabwe as reported recently in the media (Mswazie, 2014 December 24; The Telegraph, 2011 October 26; Allen, 2017 June 23; Newsday, 2014 May 20; Newsday, 2018 July 13; Agbo, 2018 November 5; Akbar, 2018 January 17; The Zimbabwe Mail, 2018 September 6; Mushangwa, 2013 July 19; Dzobo, 2014 March 24; Newsday, 2019 January 31). These media sources report very current instances where some humans had incestuous sex, sex with goats, donkeys and dogs. In fact, recently, some United Nations peacekeepers in the Central African Republic stripped naked and tied some African girls to trees before forcing them to have sex with dogs (Nhemachena, 2024a; Genovese, 2018). Besides, colonialists conveniently theorized prostitution as freedom from African cultural ancestral structures which they depicted as oppressive because they enforce sexual normativity and morals.

The reason why colonialists denigrated and decentered African ancestral metaphysics of sexuality, including sexual normativity, is evident in colonial practices. During colonialism, African women and girls were used to sexually satisfy colonial and imperial soldiers who were far away from their own wives - staying in the metropolitan centers; colonial patrons of brothels also sought to make huge profits by employing African girls and women as prostitutes who were often not paid for the sexual services they provided (Muchomba, 2014; Tiquet, 2020 June 22; Irving, 2021 July 26; White, 1990; Aderinto, 2015; Kozma, 2017; Kropiwnicki, 2012; Odeke & Onuoha, 2021; Heyningen, 1984). The argument here is that such sexualities which subvert African cultural normativity are considered polluting and dangerous in African metaphysics. African ancestral metaphysics expect African women and girls to get married, raise children within marriage and family institutions. However, colonialists depicted African cultures as oppressive, they depicted African ancestors as demons, and they urged African women and girls to rebel against these supposed demons and oppressive cultures in the name of freedoms to be prostituted by the colonialists.

In African ancestral metaphysics of sexuality, prostitution is not considered as freedom but it is understood to be polluting in the sense of attracting alien dirty spirits. Even traditional healers were expected to have [sexual] purity to protect themselves and their clients from alien spirits of dirtiness and pollution which brought illnesses and dangers to humans. Writing about the significance of purity for African healers, Mwandayi (2011, p. 246) observes that:

Extra purity is demanded of healers when it comes to the healing of a seriously ill patient. In such cases, it is demanded of them to abstain from sexual intercourse...Purity is demanded also of the *mukumbi* (healer's personal assistant). Before he/she is enrolled, he/she is cleansed of impurities with water, incense and medicated smoke. Even when it comes to the selection of a possible host, the spirit is believed to look for the purity of the heart and a character that fits its own. No form of impurity also is entertained in the hut where a medium performs his/her healing sessions otherwise that would invoke the spirit's anger down upon the perpetrator. Misbehavior, for example, as in the sexual excesses of young men and women is said to annoy the spirits also.

The metaphysics of sexuality is also underscored in ceremonies and rituals. For instance, African "rainmaking" ceremonies required sexual and other forms of purity because African ancestors and *Mwari* (God) do not like [sexual] impurities and pollution. Writing about such ceremonies in Zimbabwe, Ombati (2017, p. 85-6) states that:

During rainmaking ceremonies, only preadolescents and post-menopausal women carry beer pots to Njelele, so as to maintain the shrine's purity and not permit defilement by married women who still experience menstrual periods.

After decentering and deconstructing African ancestral metaphysics of sexuality, colonialists introduced the commercialization of sex, in the form of prostitution, to vulnerable Africans who had not even commercialized their own economies which remained subsistence based. Prostitution was part of the bioeconomy of colonialism which sought to exploit and benefit from the biological bodies of African women and girls that were turned into prostitutes. Colonial governments dispossessed Africans of their land, levied taxes on Africans, established inequitable urban housing, they threw African women into privation such that they ended up in the colonial prostitution industries that emerged with colonialism.

Colonized women were "made available" to colonial soldiers and were made to stay near colonial military barracks; colonialists established dedicated locations for colonized women whom they had turned into prostitutes; brothels were integrated within military barracks; colonial owners of brothels exploited the colonized women who they turned into prostitutes; the colonized women were denied payment collected by the colonial patrons of the brothels; prostitution was also a result of transformations of subsistence economy, it was a result of intrusion of colonial capitalism and the attendant proletarianization of Africans whose lives were being commercialized and degraded (Muchomba, 2014; Kropiwnicki, 2012). Sexuality ceased to be regulated by African ancestral metaphysical normativity, rather, sexuality fell to the metaphysics of Western capitalism which placed imperatives of commerce and profit ahead of African ancestral imperatives of [sexual] morality, purity, ethics, cultural normativity and customs.

Having lost their land and other material resources to colonialists, vulnerable Africans are increasingly resorting to prostitution, including homosexuality; in some parts of Zimbabwe, prostitution is reported as the main source of income; child prostitution is on the rise in many parts of Zimbabwe, and Africa more broadly (University World News, 2010 November 7; Dzenga, 2022 November 30; Mabvurira et al., 2017; New Zimbabwe, 2022 December 4; Ncube, 2022 April 20). In fact, some, including a former Zimbabwean minister, have recently advocated for the legalization of prostitution (Zulu, 2015 May 27; Vinga, 2023 November 23). Some thinkers describe the prostitution as freedom and as occasions for African women to exercise their sexual autonomy from “patriarchal” marriages and families (Odeke & Onuoha, 2021). The point here is that nonnormative sexual practices do not signify freedom but privation brought about by the colonialists.

When one is deprived of material means of production and subsistence, one is forced to wait indefinitely for conventional marriage because wait-hood implies possession of the material means to wait. Yet, not waiting implies possibilities of contracting sexual metaphysical pollution without the blessings of ancestors. Africans knew that to enter the ancestral world and to be accorded the position of an ancestor, they needed to live exemplary lives including in sexual matters. Africans conceive of the parallel world of ancestors to which those who will have lived exemplary human lives, and for whom appropriate funerary rituals have been conducted will be admitted (Onyedima, 2008; Garbett, 1998; Mararike, 1999; Chitando, 2016).

Exemplary lives entail a life where they followed African culture as prescribed and set by ancestors who are known as the guardians of morals, ethics, etiquette, normativity, laws and the souls of their descendants. Because ancestors are interested in their descendants and in the continuity of their lineages, exemplary life which is the basis for admission into the ancestral world also includes having married and reproduced the lineage during one’s lifetime. Those that die unmarried and without children are not admitted into the ancestral world because they would not have lived exemplary lives (Kwayedza, 2015 March 3; Mhaka, 2014; Chitakure, 2021).

In fact, those that died without being married and without having children were buried with maize kernel (*guri*), with a stick, with a rat or a cooking stick, or knobkerrie; for example, the rat was put on the sexual organs of the corpse of one who died unmarried and without children (Kwayedza, 2015 March 13; Mhaka, 2014; Nyanungo, 2018) – a female rat for a male who died unmarried and a male rat for a female who died unmarried; then words such as ‘You...here is your wife/husband, do not come back to trouble us’ are uttered over the grave (Mhaka, 2014). In other parts of Zimbabwe, the rat is placed in the rectum of a man or woman who died unmarried; a spinster who died unmarried is buried with a *citrillus lanatus* (*shamba*) tied to her back to represent a child; some bury a bachelor who died unmarried with a sausage fruit (*mvera*) representing wife or child; a stick could also be inserted into the anus of an unmarried man or woman during burial; those who died unmarried were given symbolic wives such as an animal, roofing pole, grinding stone or any other symbol so that their spirits would not return to cause havoc

to the living or to generate family trends of failures to get married and to reproduce children (Chitakure, 2021).

Among the Shona people, spirits of those who died unmarried or without children do not become ancestors; the spirit of an unmarried person is disqualified from enjoying the status of an ancestor; instead, the spirit of a person who died unmarried was ordered not to come back to the human world as an ancestor; those who died unmarried or without children were denied the ceremony of *kurova guva* (a ceremony to turn one into an ancestor); the spirits of those who die unmarried or without children stayed in the veldt or the place where they were interred; besides, people for whom full funerary rituals have not been performed are considered to be still dirty or unclean because no cleansing would have been done yet (Chitakure, 2021; Mwandayi, 2011).

What this means is that the spirits of those that died unmarried and without children remain unclean and dirty because they are not given full funeral rituals; such spirits are polluting and dangerous when they return to generate trends of failures to marry and have children. For the Shona people, death is a journey to a better world where they would live forever; the ancestors live in that better world but they are not indifferent to the world of the living; also, sorcerers, witches and murderers do not receive full funeral rituals because they are not allowed to return as ancestors; the Shona people believe that ancestors are God's lieutenants (Mwandayi, 2011; Nhemachena, 2017). To return as an ancestor, one must live virtuous, normal, conventional and moral lives in terms of ancestral lore.

In the ancestral metaphysics of sexuality, ancestors require moral conduct and purity. Ancestors are understood to help in ensuring one's character is good provided that the person does not offend them; ancestors are considered to deserve *mombe yechimanda* (a cow in appreciation) when their daughters and granddaughters get married while they are still virgins; the Shona people and ancestors look down upon *unzenza* (sexually licentious practices); those that become sexually loose are described as wells into which various objects can fall; for Africans, sex was not for recreation but for procreation and so it had to be done at the appropriate time in terms of ancestral chronos and kairos; sexual immorality reduced chances of getting married; also, immorality deprived ancestors of *mombe yechimanda*; sexual immorality was a disgrace; also, sexual immorality defiled the young people such that during marriage rituals those that had lost purity through premarital sex were symbolized through a coin with a hole at the center or a blanket or cloth which was pierced; young people who defiled others were fined and ordered to pay damages; sex was considered sacred; and, a woman/girl's body was considered sacred such that it could only be seen naked by a man who would have paid *lobola* or marriage consideration (Kambarami, 2006; Bhana & Matswetu, 2023; Makaudze, 2015b).

With the colonial deconstruction and decentering of African ancestors, African women and girls' bodies ceased to be sacred. And because some Africans no longer know the traditional herbs and medicines which were used to modulate and regulate sexuality

(Nhemachena, 2024b) some African bodies have become circulating references in the realm of sexuality as they switch from one partner to the next. In the metaphysics of sexuality, the sanctity of a woman's body was extended to the sanctity of her properties. With ancestral sanctification, anyone who violated a woman's or girl's body attracted spiritual sanctions in the form of avenging spirits. African bodies, and properties, were protected through ancestral metaphysical sanctifications. Even the kitchens in which women worked were considered so sacred that traditional rituals were performed in those kitchens.

When the Shona people offered to their ancestors, they did so in the kitchens. At the centers of the kitchens are hearths where the fire is lit and where the African mother prepares food. In front of the hearth is a *chikuva* (shelve); the *chikuva* is constructed as a platform and it is treated by the Shona people as a sacred place. The kitchen is treated as a temple. The heads of the family preside over this altar, meaning the sacred *chikuva*. In the kitchen there are also special utensils like *gano* (axe) and sacred plates for the ancestors (*ndiro dzevadzimu*) are kept in the kitchen. The kitchen is the woman's sanctuary and even the husband is prohibited from removing utensils from it without the blessings of the woman.;The name *chikuva* means a small grave; it is a place where the family communes with the ancestors. The Shona people also believe that their family spirits are always with them as long as they have good morals. Thus, the Shona and Ndebele people value marriage and not extramarital or premarital sex (Mahohoma, 2020; Gwandure, 2012).

Whereas colonialists condemned the kitchen as a private and miserable place for women to stay in, the rondavel kitchen in Shona metaphysics is not a private sphere because it is the place where ancestors meet with the living during the commemorations. As officiants and occupants of the sacred kitchens, women were sanctified and protected by ancestors whose traffic and intensity were felt within this domain. In fact, the vulnerability of women and girls existed outside the African kitchens, and not in them. Away from the sacred kitchens, there was vulnerability to rapists, colonial sexual exploiters, witches and sorcerers who polluted the women and girls.

3. WITCHES AND METAPHYSICS OF SEXUAL POLLUTION

While ancestors protect descendants and help them to keep good morals including sexual morality, witches and alien spirits fight to subvert and invert morality, including sexual morality. The alien spirits which are called *mashavi* possess their hosts haphazardly and they bestow them with skills, including for witchcraft and prostitution; *mashavi* include *shavi rekuhura* and *shavi rekuroya* (alien spirits of prostitution and alien spirits of witchcraft respectively). Important to note here is that witches are the antithesis of what it is to be human and of what it means to be an ancestor. Witches eat human flesh; witches kill others; witches use human body parts; they oppose marriages, they oppose family harmony, and they oppose cultural normativity.

Besides, witches keep and use nonhuman familiars such as hyenas, ant-bears, baboons, monkeys, cats, owls and snakes which they also have sex with as if they are companions. Witches are possessed by alien spirits which oppose ancestral spirits and cultural normativity. Such alien spirits may or may not become hereditary. An alien or foreigner's spirit is the spirit of a person from another country or clan who died uncared for or perhaps was not properly buried according to their customs. The spirit of such a person may wander restlessly until it settles on someone (Chavunduka, 1980; Simmons, 2000; Gelfand, 1959). There are also alien spirits of Europeans and North Americans who died in Africa (Gelfand, 1959) and such spirits of Europeans include that of the British archimperialist and homosexual, Cecil John Rhodes, who decided to be buried at the, now defiled, *Mwari* Shrine in the Matopo Hills of Zimbabwe (Mungwini, 2019; Nhemachena, 2022, 2024b; Gwini & Marangwanda, 2021). Writing about the alien spirits of Europeans and North Americans in Zimbabwe, Gelfand (1959, p. 121) notes that:

The same is said of the *varungu* (Europeans) who entered Mashonaland in former days to look for gold or hunt for game. Many died in these strange parts and their disturbed spirits wandered about until they settled on their selected mediums...they eventually settled upon innocent, unsuspecting Mashona who were more or less forced to accept the restless spirits and come to terms with them.

Whereas African ancestors ensured that the bodies of their descendants were sacred, witches and invasive alien spirits erode such sacredness rendering the Shona bodies open and vulnerable to immoral behaviors, including sexual immorality. Indeed, when colonialists arrived in Zimbabwe, they deliberately desecrated the ancestral sacred shrines; this deprived Africans of their ancestral protection and opened spaces for alien spirits and spirits of witches to enter African spaces and bodies (Nhemachena, 2022). Also, colonialists dug up the sacred graves and groves of African ancestors. At Great Zimbabwe, for instance, graves were dug up and the colonialists stole grave goods including jewelry and gold with which African ancestors had been buried. Besides, the colonialists buried their own fellows at the Great Zimbabwe shrine and at the Matopo Hills shrine which were African sacred shrines. Precolonial Africans used to hear the voices of their ancestors and the voice of God at Great Zimbabwe and Matopo Hills which are now defiled (Fontein, 2006; Nhemachena, 2023; Mushonga, 2006).

As Mary Douglas (1966) explains, “pollution and dirt” refer to things that are out of place, in wrong places and or mixed up. These become polluted and dirty at a metaphysical level. Historically, to avoid metaphysical pollution and danger, Africans asked their ancestors before they did anything, including before they married and before they buried a corpse. The point was to ensure that everything was placed in its proper place, including at a metaphysical level. With colonial demonization of African ancestors,

defilement of ancestral shrines, defilement of African bodies, banishment of ancestral rites and offerings, demonization of African traditional songs and with colonialists dispossessing Africans of livestock, Africans were disabled to connect with their ancestors to get metaphysical protection (Nhemachena, 2023). To retain metaphysical protection, Africans respected ancestral time known as *nguva yevadzimu* such that the time for marriage and sexual activities corresponded with ancestral time rather than with instinctual time of animalistic spirits.

Nguva yevadzimu refers to time as set in the ancestral world by ancestral spiritual guardians. Colonialists imposed their own time on Africans, and this pushed the Africans out of alignment with the time of the ancestral world. Among the Shona people, everything that one did needed to be aligned to the ancestral world and this is why Africans would always inform (*kusuma*) their ancestors before they embarked on anything. When one travelled, one had to inform one's ancestors; also, when one was about to get married, one had to inform one's ancestors; when one was getting betrothed, one had to inform one's ancestors; when one was about to build a house, one had to inform one's ancestors and even when spouses were about to have sex they recited praise names for ancestors of each other.

These ancestral practices helped to prevent sexual exploitation and sexual violence. It was almost impossible to rape because one needed to first inform ancestors (*kusuma*) and to sing ancestral praise names – and any would-be victim of rape would naturally have time to run away. Even in possible cases of murder, assault, domestic violence, adultery, fornication, extramarital sex and buggery one would have needed to inform ancestors and to sing ancestral praise names – and being guardians of morals, ethics, norms, etiquette and conventions, ancestors would decline to approve immoral activities. Put differently, the ancestral requirement to *kusuma* and to sing ancestral praise names before doing anything, including sex, was intended to ensure ancestral protection and it was intended to ensure that Africans did not engage in sex indiscriminately and with people whose ancestry they did not know about. It effectively prevented prostitution, adultery, fornication, extramarital sex, buggery, sexual exploitation and domestic violence – and it ensured sexual purity and marriageability of descendants. Because everything had to be done within *nguva yevadzimu*, it follows that what ancestors did not approve of could not be done because they would not make time for what they did not approve.

Without ancestral metaphysics of sexuality, defiled African bodies are now circulating between different partners because of absence of stability in sexual relationships. As the defiled and vulnerable bodies move from one partner to the next, the chances of attracting marriage considerations are ever diminishing. Whereas colonialists promoted their ancestors to the positions of saints, Africans have been forced to dump their own ancestors – and in the process they lost ancestral sanctification and ancestral metaphysical protection; whereas colonialists have not dumped their own cultures, Africans have been forced to dump their cultures – and in the process they became

vulnerable to sexual exploitation including by colonialists who tricked them into dumping their own ancestors; indeed kings and queens are still powerful in Europe and monarchies still rule as guardians of European cultures, even as Africans are sadly forced to demonize and depose their own chiefs and kings (Nhemachena & Warikandwa, 2019). Indeed, colonial brothels turned African women and girls into circulating references always shifting from one partner to the next. The argument here is that African sexuality lost alignment with ancestral time when colonialists imposed colonial metaphysics and colonial names on Africans.

4. METAPHYSICS OF TIME AND NAMING PRACTICES: NHODZERA

Drawing on the anthropology and sociology of time (Kirtsoglou & Simpson, 2020; Gokmenoglu, 2022; Wajcman, 2008; Suckert, 2022; Gell, 1992), we argue that colonial time was misaligned to African ancestral metaphysics of time, in the sense of time as set in the ancestral world. With colonialism, Africans got trapped in long waitness because they needed to get jobs to earn money to marry. Having been dispossessed of their fertile land and livestock, including cattle which they originally used in marriage processes, Africans got trapped in long waitness to get married (Nhemachena, 2024e). In the absence of material means of subsistence, sexual partners become circulating references in the sense of moving from one partner to the next, which poses the danger of sexual metaphysical pollution in African ontologies and cosmologies. In other words, after missing ancestral time, one risks becoming a circulating reference in the realm of sexuality – trapped in waitness for marriage while ironically ever-circulating among different partners.

The disjuncture between ancestral time and colonial time affected the ancestral metaphysics of sexuality in that the descendants who observed colonial time got misaligned with ancestral time. Some occupied zones of perpetual waitness because they had missed ancestral time, in the sense of *kairos*. Because colonialists dictated time, Africans experienced colonial chronocracy in the form of colonial power to dictate time. Colonialists dismissed African ancestral time. Colonialists began to dictate their own time – which is what is meant by colonial chronocracy. Colonial chronocracy is well captured by Kirtsoglou & Simpson (2020, p. 24) thus:

...as all other forms of violence, chronocracy saturates our everyday existence, and from there it is capable of fleshing out the sinister side of our most positive faculties like imagination, creativity, potentiality, immanence and agency. When chronocracy becomes imaginative it finds all sorts of new and creative ways of planting itself in our worlds. It turns potentiality and immanence into insecurity, it converts endurance and maintenance into stagnation, it adjusts development and growth into

tyrannical structures of accumulation, exploitation... it makes hope feel like a waiting room. Hijacked by chronocracy, hope becomes a timescape composed of the ruins of our present, of our dead dreams and of closed-off possibilities...

The problem with anthropologists is that they have tended to rely on colonial time (Fabian, 2014; Pina-Cabral, 2000) while ignoring both African time and the time of the ancestral worlds. In fact, anthropologists have tended to shy away from focusing on time as a subject in its own right; some anthropologists have tended to assume that the timescapes of the colonized peoples are circular simply because they perform world-renewing rituals; however, if time was circular then there would be no need to perform world-renewing rituals (Munn, 1992; Gell, 1992; 1998; Whyte, 2018). Even sociologists have tended to shy away from investigating time as a subject in its own right (Lewis & Weigart, 1990; Tada, 2019; Caldarovic, 2009; Bergman, 1992). Increasingly becoming important in sociology and anthropology, time is becoming central in studies of anticipation, studies of the future and studies of foresight (Karlsen et al., 2010; Strzelecka, 2013) including in the realm of sexuality that is increasingly afflicted with waitness and anxieties about the future.

Africans made efforts to please their ancestors so that they would welcome them into the ancestral world when time to die arrived. They ensured that they stuck to sexual mores, ethics, etiquette and conventions, good behavior, sexual normativity and they named their children after ancestors. Descendants were named after their ancestors so that they would take after them in terms of what the Shona people call *nhodzera*, meaning to take after the person after whom one is named. In *nhodzera*, a descendant would behave like the ancestor he/she is named after. The point is that there are metaphysical implications to naming because naming connected Africans to the ancestral world, yet European slave owners and colonialists renamed some Africans after nonhuman animals and after European personages in ways that disrupted the African connections to the ancestral world. Abel et al. (2019, pp. 336-360) aptly capture how enslaved Africans were renamed thus:

After being registered, the captives were branded on the arm, chest, or thigh with the initials of the company that had bought them. Once transferred to the slave ships, they were chained up and made to lie below deck in cramped and filthy conditions...From the perspective of colonial administrators in the New World colonies, incoming captives arrived nameless, and it was the duty of their first owner to assign them the formal name by which they would be identified in official records...Renaming constituted an act of erasure, underscoring the rupture between the people they had been and the non-people they

were to become...In Jamaican slave society the names took on new, pejorative meanings – no longer functioning as part of a dynamic system that created links among peers and across generations but instead serving as racial stereotypes...In slavery....naming is largely a one-sided act, either purely for identification purposes or for denigration, for imposing social death by severing earlier social networks and forging new ones...During and after the Middle Passage, slaveholders were usually keen to rename their slaves, often with names not unlike those applied to livestock, and indeed, slaves were considered “chattel”...The slaves were deformed with the new name, torn from their former social environments...

The point in the foregoing is that naming has the potential to generate colonial metaphysical misalignments which have implications for one’s sexuality. This is why Africans named their children after their ancestors to ensure metaphysical alignments to their ancestral worlds and to the sexual normativity the ancestors stood for. Ancestral guardians protected descendants from metaphysical abductions by alien spirits which decenter and disrupt sexual normativity.

5. ALIEN SPIRITS, WAITHOOD AND MARRIAGES IN AFRICA

Africans whose “I” has been hijacked by alien spirits begin to mistake the sexuality of the invading alien spirits for their own personal sexualities. The hijacked Africans begin to feel oppressed, dominated and uncomfortable in their own cultural normativity because the invading alien spirit that has hijacked them does not belong to the African culture. By extension, Africans who have been hijacked by invading alien spirits would even begin to feel uncomfortable in their own bodies because the alien spirits that have hijacked them did not have African bodies.

Africans who have been hijacked by alien spirits feel uncomfortable in African cultural normativity and in African bodies precisely because the alien spirit did not belong to African culture, to African bodies and to African sexual *boni mores*. Thus, alien spirits are spirits of inversions and subversions. They subvert the bodies which they have hijacked; they subvert the cultural normativity which they have invaded; the alien spirits seek to invert and subvert the gender and sex of the African victims whose bodies they have lodged in. They subvert the marriages and families of the victims whose bodies they have hijacked. Of course, the hijacking alien spirits may justify their invasions by pretending and/or claiming that they want to help the victim whose body they have hijacked.

Victims of alien spiritual invasions risk addressing the freedom and autonomy of the alien spirits as their own freedoms and autonomies. In African ancestral metaphysics, a person who has lost ancestral metaphysical protection does not thereby become free or

autonomous. Rather the person becomes open and vulnerable to abductions by alien spiritual forces that invade and begin to use the body of the victim to claim freedom and autonomy for themselves. Alien spirits subvert sexual normativity, in the process, casting their African victims into perpetual waitness for African conventional marriages and sexuality.

The ways in which Africans have been hijacked by pantheons of foreign or alien spirits are clearly explicated by Behrend and Luig (1999, p. xiii) thus:

The disenchantment of the modern world and the disappearance of spirits, as foretold by Westerners, has not taken place, either at home or in other parts of the world. In Africa as well as Europe, many spirits and their mediums are part of the local as well as global or transglobal cultures. Thus, we find Christian spirits named Hitler and Mussolini or King Bruce after Bruce Lee, the Kung-Fu actor, in a pantheon of new Christian holy spirits in Northern Uganda...

Thus, alien spiritual *coup de tats* disrupted African ancestral metaphysics of sexuality. In fact, colonialists brought with them their many other gods and goddesses after which they named days of the week and months of the year. For instance, the month of January is named after, *Janus* who is known as a god of beginnings, god of duality, god of doors, or god of gates; similarly, the month of February is named after a goddess *Februa* who is known as an overseer and purifier of things. The goddess *Februa* is responsible for cleansing rituals and for sacrifice. *Februa* is a goddess of lamentations, mourning the dead and placating ghosts of the dead. Besides, the month of March is dedicated to a god of war called Mars or *Martius*. In addition, the month of April is dedicated to the goddess *Aphrodite* the goddess of sexual love; the month of May is dedicated to a goddess called *Maia*; and, the month of June is dedicated to the goddess *Juno* (Nhemachena, 2017; Davenport, 2018; Silver, 2019).

Similarly, days of the week are dedicated to European gods and goddesses. Tuesday is dedicated to a god called *Twi* who is associated with warfare. Wednesday is dedicated to a god called *Woden* who is associated with eloquence, travel and guardianship over the dead. The day Thursday is dedicated to a god called *Thor* known to be a god of thunder, and Friday is dedicated to a goddess called *Frig* who is associated with sex, love and affection (Rosenfield, 1994; Ross, 2018; Nhemachena, 2017). Indeed, some of the European gods and goddesses are guardians and patrons of homosexuality yet colonialists named colonial subjects after these gods and goddesses whose operations oppose the sexual morality and normativity which African ancestors desire (Nhemachena, 2024b).

With such spiritual and metaphysical *coup de tats*, the African ancestral metaphysics of sexuality has been upended such that sexual normativity is increasingly becoming an exception rather than the rule (Odimegwu et al., 2018; Obeng-Hinne & Kpoor, 2021 Pauli, 2019). Cohabitation is becoming a norm as African marriages are

being upended; marriage considerations are losing traction as human sexuality is becoming indistinct from animal sexuality; rape, domestic violence, poor relationship quality and non-marital unions are increasing (Mavaza & Madekufamba, 2021; Obeng-Hinne & Kpoor, 2021). Because colonialists robbed Africans of hundreds of thousands of cattle, goats and sheep which constituted means for marriage considerations (Nhemachena, 2021, 2023; Jalata, 2011; Gewald, 2004), many Africans can no longer afford to get married in ways recognized by their cultures (Shoko, 2007; Mwandayi, 2017; Makaudze, 2015a).

Compounding metaphysical vulnerability in matters of African sexuality, some NGOs oppose African culture, they oppose African sexual normativity and they oppose African marriages. In fact, there is a risk that African sexualities are increasingly becoming indistinct from the sexualities of nonhuman animals. Without *hunhu*, morality and cultural normativity (Makaudze, 2015b; Viriri & Viriri, 2018; Manyonganise, 2015; Chireshe & Chireshe, 2010; Togarasei & Chitando, 2021; Mutswairo, 1996; Holleman, 1969; Gelfand, 1967), African sexuality is being turned into posthumanist sexualities and postanthropocentric sexualities wherein morality and ancestral sexual normativity are upended (Nhemachena, 2024f; Ourkiya, 2020; Tallbear & Willey, 2019; Basu, 2021; Liu, 2015). In fact, queer theorists and posthumanists argue that there should be no binaries between human sexuality and animal sexuality (Shabbar, 2019; Durkin, 2022; Ferrando, 2013; Milligan, 2011).

However, the Shona people would say *haasi munhu* or *haasi munhu chaiye* (does not have *hunhu* and is not a good person/human) (Viriri & Viriri, 2018; Manyonganise, 2015) to someone who has no sexual and cultural normativity – and is sexually behaving like an animal. Having been dispossessed of their material resources during the colonial era, Africans now lack resources to humanize their marriages and to distinguish their sexuality from animal sexuality. They are now forced to wait indefinitely for marriages conducted in terms of African norms.

Waiting refers to engagements with colonial structural and institutional conditions that force people to wait in matters of sexuality. Waiting is often a weapon to make existence intolerable for certain groups of people. Waiting places certain groups of people in temporal relations where the outcome is uncertain. Waiting limits productive use of time and such waiting is costly. In everyday life, generally, waiting is often bound to specific places like shelters, waiting rooms, waiting halls and the waiting person may be part of a community of fellow waiting people. Waiting may be in a queue and some people make it clear to others that they are waiting and they may wait in publicly accessible places to demonstrate to others that they are waiting. Waiting produces societal symbols, timetables and collective schedules; at times, waiting is something that humans do not realize they are doing (Bandak & Janeja, 2018; Ayab, 2020; Price, 2021). In other words, waiting, including sexual waithood, is a central aspect of colonial chronocracy.

The phenomenon of waiting in the realm of sexuality is often taken for granted. There is need for research on the waiting places, social waiting, unexpected waiting and alternatives to waiting including killing time while waiting. It is necessary to examine how people entertain themselves while waiting in realms of sexuality. Also, it is essential to examine how technology, including humanoid sex robots, has provided alternatives to waiting or sexual waithood. It is important to interrogate the functions of real and metaphorical waiting props such as rails, ropes, connected poles, floor markings such as arrows, floor signs and signs directing people to how, where and what to expect while waiting including waiting for marriage. Scholars have also noted the necessity of examining whether people wait while - really and metaphorically - standing or sitting or both, that is sit-wait or stand-wait or combo-waiting.

Thus, there is need to investigate structures of waiting which provide order, organization, formation, flexibility and cultural norms while waiting. Besides, it is important to explain why some people wait in undesignated areas. It is also essential to examine how [cultural] architects construct wait structures which individuals may resist or follow while waiting. And it is imperative to examine what red flags are raised for those that wait outside the designated areas of sexual waithood. Also important are observations on what adventures those that are waiting engage in, whether they really or metaphorically wait in line or not (Price, 2021; Lyman & Scott, 1989). By disrupting African metaphysics of sexuality, colonialists induced sexual waithood – and while waiting, some humans adopt animalistic nonnormative sexualities in the global US\$30 billion sex industry.

Although Honwana (2013, 2014) argues that it is failed postcolonial neo-liberal economic policies, bad governance and political instability in Africa that have pushed African youths into waithood, we note that [sexual] waithood in Africa emanates from colonial dispossession and exploitation. For Honwana, young people in Africa can no longer support themselves and their families. Most young people are living in a period of suspension between childhood and adulthood – which is a state of limbo that is replacing conventional adulthood. The African youths lack jobs; they have deficient education, are unable to obtain work and become independent. The young people are waiting for adulthood; they are no longer children but they are not yet adults. Chronological age may define them as adults but they have not been able to attain the social markers of adulthood because they cannot marry and support their families as adults would do. What we mean here is that the history of waithood must be traced from the colonial era.

Since the colonial era, Africans are waiting for the return of their ancestors who were banished as demons by colonialists. Africans are waiting for the return of African sexual normativity which became difficult after colonialists dispossessed them of their material means for marriage. Besides, Africans are waiting for the return of African marriages banished as oppressive, patriarchal, demonic and so on. Also, Africans are waiting for reconnections to their ancestral worlds which suffered spiritual *coup de tats* when invasive alien spirits entered their metaphysical spaces. In other words, Africans

are waiting for the return of their metaphysical protection which was destroyed by the colonial defilement and desecration of African shrines and bodies. Africans are waiting for metaphysical and physical fortresses to cover and protect their bodies. Because they did not want to be ruled at a metaphysical level by African ancestors, colonialists dismissed the African ancestors as demons – and because they did not want to be ruled at the physical level by African chiefs and kings, colonialists dismissed them as patriarchal, savage, backward and oppressive. Colonialists wanted African bodies and sexuality to be open and vulnerable at both physical and metaphysical levels.

6. CONCLUSION

Arguing that ancestors offered metaphysical protection and security to African sexuality, this paper has also contended that colonialists have created, and profited from, metaphysical and physical openness and vulnerability of African bodies. Put differently, the argument is that the colonial demonization of African ancestors, as demons, was designed to disrupt and decenter ancestors and the metaphysical protection they provided to their descendants. With African normative sexualities, including marriages, having been disrupted, many Africans have been forced into sexual waitness where they indefinitely wait for conventional African marriages. In this regard, the colonial and imperial global sex industry needed to conscript, enroll and mobilize African women and girls, which tasks would have been very difficult in the presence of ancestral sanctifications and protection at metaphysical levels.

REFERENCES

- Abel, S., Tyson, G. F. & Palsson, G. (2019). From enslavement to emancipation: Naming practices in the Danish West Indies. *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 61(2), 332-365.
- Aderinto, S. (2015). Journey to work: Transnational prostitution in colonial British West Africa. *Journal of the History of Sexuality*, 24 (1), 99-124.
- Agbo, N. (2018 November 5). 33-year old South African man found guilty of sleeping with a goat. *The Guardian* <https://guardian.ng/life/33-year-old-south-african-man-found-guilty-of-sleeping-with-a-goat>
- Akbar, J. (2018 January 17). Animal sex beast raped his mum's two goats to death in sickening two hour attack. *The Sun* <https://www.thesun.co.uk/news/5360819/animal-sex-beast-raped-mums-goat-jailed-kenya>
- Allen, F. (2017 June 23). Donkey owner who caught randy freak having sex with his animal is demanding tribal leaders force him to marry the baffled beast. *The Sun* <https://www.thesun.co.uk/news/3869168/donkey-owner-sex-demands-marry-animal-south-africa>
- Aschwanden, H. (1982). *Symbols of Life: An Analysis of the Consciousness of the Karanga*. Gweru: Mambo Press.
- Ayab, R. (2020). Doing waiting: An ethnomethodological analysis. *Journal of Contemporary Ethnography*, 49(4)
- Ball, P. (2023 August 21). The big idea: Should we colonise other planets. *The Guardian* <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2023/aug/21/the-big-idea-should-we-colonise-other-planets>
- Bandak, A & Janeja, M. K. (2018). Introduction: Worth the wait. In M. K. Janeja & A. Bandak (eds). *Ethnographies of Waiting: Doubt, Hope and Uncertainty*. London & New York: Routledge.
- Basu, P. (2021). Posthuman embodiment and queer identity in Frankenstein and the life cycle of software objects. *Consortium: An International Journal of Literary and Cultural Studies*, 1 (2), 44-51.
- Battaglia, D., Valentine, D & Olson, V. (2015). Relational space: An earthly installation. *Cultural Anthropology*, 30 (2), 245-256.
- Behrend, H & Luig, U. (1999). Introduction. In H. Behrend & U. Luig (eds). *Spirit Possession, Modernity & Power in Africa*. Oxford: James Currey Ltd.
- Bergmann, W. (1992). The Problem of time in sociology: An overview of the literature on the state of theory and research on the sociology of time, 1900-82. *Time & Society*, 1(81), 81-134.
- Bhana, D & Matswetu, V. (2023). Girls under surveillance: Emerging Zimbabwean Parents on young people's sexual health. *Health Education Journal*, 82 (6), 623-635.
- Billings, L. (2019). Colonizing other planets is a bad idea. *Futures*, 110, 44-46.

- Burns, M. (2020). Reclaiming indigenous sexual being: Sovereignty and decolonization through sexuality. *The Arbutus Review*, 11 (1)
- Caldarovic, O. (2009). Sociology of time – Overview of major ideas and concepts. *Socijalna Ekologija*, 18 (3-4), 215-235.
- Chavunduka, G. L. (1980). Witchcraft and the law in Zimbabwe. *Zambezia* 8 (2), 129-147.
- Chireshe, E. & Chireshe, R. (2010). Lobola: The Perceptions of Great Zimbabwe University students. *The Journal of Pan African Studies*, 3 (9), 211-221.
- Chitakure, J. (2021). *Death Rituals among the Karanga of Zimbabwe: praxis, Significance and Changes*. Wipf and Stock Publishers
- Chitando, E. (2016). *African Traditions in the Study of Religion in Africa: Emerging Trends, Indigenous Spirituality and the Interface with Other World Religions*. Routledge.
- Currier, A. (2012). The aftermath of decolonization: Gender and sexual dissidence in postindependence Namibia. *Signs*, 37 (2), 441-467.
- Davenport, C. (2018 January 10). Explainer: Where do the names of our months come from? *The Conversation* <https://theconversation.com/explainer-where-do-the-names-of-our-months-come-from>
- Douglas, M. (1966). *Purity and Danger: An Analysis of the Concept of Pollution and Taboo*. London and New York: Routledge
- Drake, N. (2023 March 13). What is the multiverse – and is there any evidence it really exists. *National Geographic* <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/science/article/what-is-the-multiverse>
- Durkin, K. (2022). Adventures in the anti-humanist dialectic: Towards the Reappropriation of Humanism. *European Journal of Social Theory*, 25 (2), 292-311.
- Dvorak, J. (2019). The Philosopher within: The daimon in Plato. *Philomathes* <https://www.apsu.edu/philomathes/Dvorakphilomathes>
- Dzenga, D. M. (2022 November 30). Child prostitution at Musiiwa a microcosm of a national problem. *NewsDay* <https://www.newsday.co.zw/amh-voices/article/200005017/child-prostitution-at-musiiwa-a-microcosm-of-a-national-problem>
- Dzobo, F. (2014 March 24). African tradition abhors incestuous relationships. *Chronicle* <https://www.chronicle.zo.zw/african-tradition-abhors-incestuous-relationships>
- Engmann, R. A. A. (2012). Under imperial eyes, black bodies, buttons, and breasts: British colonial photography and Asante “Fetish Girls”. *African Arts* 45 (2), 46-57.
- Evola, J. (1983). *The Metaphysics of Sex*. New York: Inner Traditions International.
- Fabian, J. (2014). *Time & the Other: How Anthropology Makes its Object*. New York: Columbia University Press.
- Ferrando, F. (2013). Posthumanism, transhumanism, Antihumanism,

- Metahumanism, and new materialism: Differences and relations. *International Journal in Philosophy, Religion, Politics and the Arts*, 8 (2), 26-32.
- Fontein, J. (2006). Silence, destruction and closure at Great Zimbabwe: Local narratives of desecration and alienation. *Journal of Southern African Studies*, 32 (4), 771-794.
- Fontein, J. (2009). The politics of the dead: Living heritage, bones and commemoration in Zimbabwe. *Association of Social Anthropologists of the UK and Commonwealth*, 1 / 2, 1027
- Garbett, K. (1998). Contrasting realities: Changing perceptions of Shona witch beliefs and practices. *Social Analysis: The International Journal of Anthropology*, 42 (2), 24-47.
- Gelfand, M. (1959). *Shona Ritual: With Special Reference to the Chaminuka Cult*. Cape Town: Juta & Co., Limited.
- Gelfand, M. (1967). The Shona attitude to sex behavior. *Nada: The Southern Rhodesian Native Affairs Department Annual*, 9 (4), 61-64.
- Gell, A. (1992). *The Anthropology of Time: Cultural Constructions of Temporal Maps and Images*. Oxford & Washington D.C.: Berg
- Gell, A. (1998). Time and Social Anthropology. *Senri Ethnological Studies*, 45, 9 – 24.
- Genovese, S. (2018). Prosecuting peacekeepers for sexual and gender-based violence in the Central African Republic. *Brooklyn Journal of International Law*, 43 (2), 609-637.
- Gewald, J. B. (2004). *Imperial Germany and the Herero of Southern Africa: Genocide and the Quest for Recompense in Genocide, War Crimes and the West: History and Complicity*. London: Zed Books.
- Gokmenoglu, B. (2022). Temporality in the social sciences: New directions for a political sociology of time. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 73 (3), 643-653.
- Graham, D. W. (2016). Socrates' mission. *BYU Studies Quarterly*, 55 (4), 141-159.
- Gwandure, C. (2012). Sexual desire and expression among girls in a traditional Shona context. *Anthropologist*, 14 (5), 415-423
- Gwini, T & Marangwanda, C. (2021). The significance of Rhodes' grave in light of the global 'Rhodes Must Fall Movement. *History of Religion, Cultural Heritage, Indigenous Ecological Knowledges and Practices*
<https://doi.org/10.1080/21681392>
- Heyningen, E. V. (1984). The social evil in the Cape Colonial 1868-1902: Prostitution and the contagious diseases act. *Journal of Southern African Studies*, 10, 170-197.
- Holleman, J. F. (1969). *Shona Customary Law: With Reference to Kinship, Marriage, the Family and Estate*. Manchester: Manchester University Press.
- Holme, C. M. (2016). The colonial roots of the racial fetishization of black women. *Black & Gold*, 2 (1 &2), 1-12.
- Honwana, A. (2013). Youth, waithood, and protest movements in Africa. International Africa Institute Lugard lecture 2013

- Honwana, A. (2014). 'Waithood': Youth transitions and social change: response to Syed Mansoob Murshed. *Development and Equity*, 28-40
- Hund, W. D., Mills, C. W. & Sebastian, S. (2016). Editorial. In W. Hund., C. Mills & S. Sebastian (eds) *Simianization: Apes, Gender, Class, and Race*. Zurich: LIT Verlag GmbH & Co. KG Wien pp. 7-18.
- Irving, H. (2021 July 26). Colonialism and sex work in French North Africa https://socialhistory.org.uk/shs_exchange/colonialism-and-sex-work-in-french-north-africa
- Jalata, A. (2011). European colonial terrorism and the incorporation of Africa into the capitalist world system. Social World Publication and Other Worlds https://trace.tennessee.edu/utk_socipuls/18
- Kambarami, M. (2006). Femininity, Sexuality and Culture: Patriarchy and female Subordination in Zimbabwe. In Understanding Human Sexuality Seminar Series University of Fort Hare, South Africa ARSRC
- Karlsen, J. E., Overland, E. F. & Karlsen, H et al. (2010). Sociological contributions to futures theory building. *Foresight*, 12 (3), 59-72.
- Kenny, P. (2003). Socratic knowledge and the daimon. *Aporia*, 13 (1), 26-40.
- Kirtsoglou, E. & Simpson, B. (2020). Introduction: The time of anthropology: Studies of contemporary chronopolitics and chronocracy. In E. Kirtsoglou and B. Simpson. (eds). *The Time of Anthropology: Studies in Contemporary Chronopolitics*. London & New York: Routledge.
- Kozma, L. (2017). Prostitution and colonial relations. In M R Garcia., L H van Voss & E van Nederveen Meerkerk (eds) *Selling Sex in the City: A Global History of Prostitution, 1600s-2000s*. BRILL
- Kropiwnicki, Z. O. D. S. (2012). The politics of child prostitution in South Africa. *Journal of Contemporary African Studies*, 30 (2), 235-265.
- Kwayedza. (2015 March 13). Vanovigwa negonzo <https://www.kwayedza.co.za/vanovigwa-negonzo/>
- Lewis, J. D. & Weigart, A. J. (1990). The structures and meanings of social time. In J. Hassard (ed). *The Sociology of Time*. London: Palgrave MacMillan.
- Lewis, S. (2020 June 18). There may be more than 36 intelligent alien civilizations in the Milky Way, Scientists say <https://www.cbcnews.com/news/alien-civilizations-intelligent-milky-way-study/>
- Lim, E. (2023 March 22). The multiverse: How we're tackling the challenges facing the theory. *The Conversation* <https://theconversation.com/the-multiverse-how-were-tackling-the-challenges-facing-the-theory>
- Liu, P. (2015). *Queer Human Rights in and Against the Two Chinas. Queer Marxism in Two Chinas*. Duke University Press.
- Lyman, S. M. & Scott, M. B. (1989). *A Sociology of the Absurd*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Mabvurira, V. et al. (2017). The realities of children in prostitution in Zimbabwe: A case of Beitbridge and Plumtree. *Child Abuse Research in South Africa*, 18 (2).

- Mahaswa, R. K. & Kim, M. S. (2023). Introducing the pluriverse of the Anthropocene: Towards an ontological politics of environmental governance in Indonesia. In A. Triyanti et al. (eds). *Environmental Governance in Indonesia*. Springer.
- Mahohoma, T & Gundani, P. H. (2020). Experiencing the sacred. *Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae*, 46 (1), 1-17.
- Makaudze, G. (2015a). Sex and the female body in Shona society. *The Journal of Pan African Studies*, 7 (8), 140-152.
- Makaudze, G. (2015b). The power of a mother in Shona milieu. *Journal for Studies in Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(1&2), 266-276.
- Manyonganise, M. (2015). Oppressive and liberative: A Zimbabwean woman's reflections on Ubuntu. *Verbum et Ecclesia*, 36(2)
- Mararike, C. G. (1999). *Survival Strategies in Rural Zimbabwe: The Role of Assets Indigenous Knowledge and Organizations*. Mond Books.
- Mavaza, M & Madekufamba, D. (2021 May 2). Why lobola should not be refundable – love must never be refunded nor measured in monetary terms. *Bulawayo24* <https://buawayo24.com/index.id-opinion-sc-columnist-byo-203095.html>
- Mhaka, E. (2014). Rituals and taboos related to death as repositories of traditional African philosophical ideas: Evidence from the Karanga of Zimbabwe. *Academic Research Journal*, 5 (4), 371-385.
- Milligan, T. (2011). The wrongness of sex with animals. *Public Affairs Quarterly*, 25 (3), 241-255.
- Mswazie, W. (2014 December 24). Man divorces wife to have sex with donkey. *Chronicle* <https://www.chronicle.co.zw/man-divorces-wife-to-have-sex-with-donkey/>
- Muchangwa, V. (2013 July 19). Upsurge of incest cases worrying. *Chronicle* <https://www.chronicle.co.zw/upsurge-incest-ceases-worrying/>
- Muchomba, F. M. (2014). Colonial policies and the rise of transactional sex in Kenya. *Journal of International Women's Studies*, 15 (2), 80-93.
- Mungwini, P. (2019). *Indigenous Shona Philosophy: Reconstructive Insights*. Grahamstown: African Humanities Publications.
- Munn, N. D. (1992). The cultural anthropology of time: critical essay. *Annu. Rev. Anthropol*, 21, 93-123.
- Mushonga, M. (2006). From 'barbarism' to civilisation': An interpretation of colonial statues and monuments in southern Africa <https://journals.co.za/doi/pdf/10.10520/AJA>
- Mutswairo, S. (1996). *An Introduction to Shona Culture*. Juta.
- Mwandayi, C. (2011). *Death and Afterlife Rituals in the Eyes of the Shona: Dialogue with Shona Customs in the Quest for Authentic Inculturation*. University of Bamberg Press
- Mwandayi, C. (2017). Towards a Reform of the Christian Understanding of Shona Traditional Marriage in Light of Ancient Israelite Marriages. *Studia Historiae Ecclesiasticae*, 43 (3), 1-26.

- Ncube, S. (2022 April 20). We will pay tax, legalise prostitution – Zvishavane sex workers. *The Mirror* <https://masvingomirror.com/we-will-pay-tax-legalise-prostitution-zvishavane-sex-workers/>
- New Zimbabwe. (2022 December 4). Sex work now the most mentioned source of income in Harare – survey shows <https://ww.newzimbabwe.com/sex-work-nwo-the-most-mentioned-source-of-income-in-harare-survey-shows>
- Newsday. (2014 May 20). Falls man faces sex with donkey charge. *Southern Eye* <https://www.newsday.co.zw/southerneye/2014/05/20/falls-man-faces-sex-donkey-charge>
- NewsDay. (2018 July 13). Men force woman into bestiality with dogs <https://www.newsday.co.zw/news/article/65136/men-force-woman-into-bestiality-with-dogs>
- Nhemachena, A & Dhakwa, E. (2022). Missionaries that muted God: Gaggling the voices of African sovereigns while enslaving and colonizing Africans. In A. Nhemachena., O. Mtapuri & M. Mawere (eds). *Sovereignty Becoming Pulverignty: Unpacking the Dark Side of Slave 4.0 Within Industry 4.0 in Twenty-First Century Africa*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG. Pp103-152.
- Nhemachena, A & Munyaradzi, M. (2024). Sexual anarchism and the homosexual agenda in Africa. In A Nhemachena., M Mawere (eds). *Special Sexual Operations? Accounting for Resistance to the Colonial Gift of Homosexuality in Twenty-First Century Africa*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG. Pp.87-122.
- Nhemachena, A & Warikandwa, T. V. (2019). *From African Peer Review Mechanisms to African Queer Review Mechanisms? Robert Gabriel Mugabe, Empire and the Decolonization of African Orifices*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG.
- Nhemachena, A. (2017). *Relationality and Resilience in a not so Relational World? Knowledge, Chivanhu and (De-)coloniality in 21st Century Conflict-Torn Zimbabwe*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG.
- Nhemachena, A. (2021). *Hakuna mhou inokumira mhuru isiyi yayo*: Examining the interface between the African body and 21st century emergent disruptive technologies. *Journal of Black Studies* 52 (8), 848-883.
- Nhemachena, A. (2023). *Chisi chako masimba mashoma/kunzi pakata sandi kunzi ridza*: Anthropological musings on the coloniality of dispossession in Africa. *Journal of Black Studies*, 54 (2), 87-110.
- Nhemachena, A. (2024a). African sexualities or imperial sexualities in Africa? Looking a “gift” horse in the mouth. In A Nhemachena., M Mawere (eds). *Special Sexual Operations? Accounting for Resistance to the Colonial Gift of Homosexuality in Twenty-First Century Africa*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG. pp 1-24
- Nhemachena, A & Mawere, M. (2024f). Sexual anarchism and the homosexual agenda in Africa. In A Nhemachena., M Mawere (eds). *Special Sexual Operations? Accounting for Resistance to the Colonial Gift of Homosexuality in Twenty-First Century Africa*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG. pp 87-122

- Nhemachena, A. (2024e). Coloniality of democracy and algocracy: in Africa: *Vanhucracy* as an Afrocentric model for politics. *Journal of Black Studies*, 55 (7), 535-553.
- Nhemachena, A. (2024d). Sex is a sigh of the oppressed creatures: The weaponization of homosexuality. In A. Nhemachena. & M. Mawere (eds). *Special Sexual Operations? Accounting for Resistance to the Colonial Gift of Homosexuality in Twenty-First Century Africa*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG. Pp. 63-86.
- Nhemachena, A. (2024c). Special sexual operations in Africa: Tracing the minorities in minority dissident sexualities. In A Nhemachena., M Mawere (eds). *Special Sexual Operations? Accounting for Resistance to the Colonial Gift of Homosexuality in Twenty-First Century Africa*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG. Pp. 25-62.
- Nhemachena, A. (2024b). The future of sexuality in Africa: Coloniality of homosexuality and how to decolonize the agenda. In A. Nhemachena. & M. Mawere (eds). *Special Sexual Operations? Accounting for Resistance to the Colonial Gift of Homosexuality in Twenty-First Century Africa*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG. Pp. 233-266.
- Nhemachena, A. (2025). Research 4.0 and the ontological turn: Implications for researching the radical alterity of witches' familiars in the twenty-first century. *Journal of Religion in Africa*, pp 1-39
- Nhemachena, A., Hlabangane, N & Matowanyika, J. Z. (2020). *Decolonizing Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) in an Age of Technocolonialism: Recentring African Indigenous Knowledge and Belief Systems*. Bamenda: Langaa RPCIG.
- Nyanungo, M. (2018). Tensions and conflicts between formal and traditional sex education in Africa-sub-Sahara. PhD Universidade de Evora
- Obeng-Hinne, R. & Kpoor, A. (2021). Cohabitation and its consequences in Ghana. *Journal of Family Issues*, 43(2)
- Odeke, F. C. & Onuoha, I. O. (2021). Globalization, prostitution and African tradition. *International Journal of International Relations, Media and Mass Communication Studies*, 7 (1), 25-40.
- Odimegwu, C. et al. (2018). Cohabitation in sub-Saharan Africa. *Southern African Journal of Demography*, 18(1), 111-170.
- Ombati, M. (2017). Rainmaking rituals: Song and dance for climate change in the making of livelihoods in Africa. *International Journal of Modern Anthropology*, 10, 74-96.
- Onyedim, E. E. (2008). The cult of ancestors: A focal point for prayers in African traditional communities. *African Journal Online* <https://www.ajol.info>
- Ourkiya, A. (2020 June 23). Queering ecofeminism: Towards an anti-far-right environmentalism <https://niche-canada.org/2020/06/23/queering-ecofeminism-towards-an-anti-far-right-environmentalism/>

- Parratt, J. (2011). Time in African traditional thought. *Religion*, 7 (2), 117-126.
- Picq, M. L. (2019). Decolonizing indigenous sexualities: Between erasure and resurgence. In M J Bosia (ed) *The Oxford Handbook of Global LGBT and Sexual Diversity Politics*. Oxford Academic
- Pina-Cabral, J. D. (2000). The ethnographic present revisited. *Social Anthropology*, 8 (3), 341-348.
- Praet, I & Salazar, J. F. (2017). Introduction: Familiarizing the extraterrestrial/making out planet alien. *Environmental Humanities*, 9 (2), 309-324
- Price, P. C. (2021). *Sociology of Waiting: How Americans Wait*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Rosenfeld, B. (1994). Religions and the Seven-day Week. *LLULL*, 17, 141-156.
- Ross, M. C. (2018 January 2). Explainer: The gods behind the days of the week. *The Conversation* <https://theconversation.com/expanier-the-gods-behind-the-days-of-the-week>
- Salazar, J. F. (2018 November 7). The cosmopolitics of outer space. Ostrom Research Workshop; Indiana University, Bloomington-November 7 2018 <https://ostromworkshop.indiana.edu/pdf/seriespapers/2018fall-res/salazar>
- Schoffleers, J. M. (ed). (2000). *Guardians of the Land*. Kachere Series.
- Shabbar, A. (2019). A queer politics of imperceptibility: A philosophy of resistance to contemporary Sexual surveillance, PhD Thesis the University of Western Ontario.
- Shoko, T. (2007). *Karanga Indigenous Religion in Zimbabwe: Health and Well-Being*. Ashgate Publishing Ltd.
- Silver, C. (2019 February 25). How did the month of February get its name <https://www.thoughtco.com/how-did-february-get-its-name>
- Simons, D. (2000). African witchcraft at the millennium: Musings on a modern phenomenon in Zimbabwe. *The Journal of the International Institute*, 7 (2)
- Smith, D & Panaitiue, I. (2016). Aping the human essence: Simianization as dehumanization. In W. Hund., C. Mills & S. Sebastian (eds). *Simianization: Apes, Gender, Class, and Race*. Zurich: LIT Verlag GmbH & Co. KG Wien, pp. 77-104.
- Strzelecka, C. (2013). Anticipatory anthropology – anthropological future study. *Prace Etnograficzne*, 41 (4), 261-269.
- Suckert, L. (2022). Back to the future. Sociological perspectives on expectations, aspirations and imagined futures. *European Journal of Sociology*, 1-36.
- Tada, M. (2019). Time as sociology's basic concepts: A perspective from Alfred Schütz's phenomenological sociology and Niklas Luhmann's social systems theory. *Time & Society*, 28(3), 995-1012.
- Tallbear, K & Willey, A. (2019). Critical relationality: Queer, indigenous and multispecies belonging beyond settler sex & nature. *Imaginations: Journal of Cross-Cultural Image Studies*, (1091), 5-15.

- Tegmark, M. (2003). Parallel universes. In J. D. Barrow., P. C. W. Davies & C. L. Harer (eds). *Science and Ultimate Reality: From Quantum to Cosmos, Honoring John Wheeler's 90th Birthday*. Cambridge University Press.
- The Telegraph. (2011 October 26). Zimbabwean man claims prostitute turned to donkey <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/newsttopics/howaboutthat/8850298/zimbabwean-man-claims-prostitute-turned-to-donkey>
- The Zimbabwe Mail. (2018 September 6). Father daughter jailed 54 months for incest <https://www.thezimbabwemail.com/law-crime/father-dughter-jailed-54-months-for-incest>
- Tiquet, R. (2020 June 22). Prostitution in a colonial setting. *Encyclopedia d' histoire numerique de l'Europe* <https://ehne.fr/en/node/12446>
- Togarasei, L & Chitando, E. (eds). (2021). *Lobola (Bridewealth) in Contemporary Southern Africa: Implications for Gender Equality*. Springer Nature
- University World News. (2010 November 7). Zimbabwe desperate students turn to prostitution <https://www.universityworldnews.com/post.php?story=20101105215346473>
- Vinga, A. (2023 November 23). Former minister says it's time Zimbabwe legalizes sex work <https://www.newzimbabwe.com/former-minister-says-its-time-zimbabwe-legalizes-sex-work/>
- Viriri, E. N. & Viriri, M. (2018). The teaching of *unhu/Ubuntu* through Shona novels in Zimbabwean secondary schools: A case for Masvingo urban district. *Journal of African Studies and Development*, 10 (8), 101-114.
- Wajcman, J. (2008). Life in the fast lane? Towards a sociology of technology and time. *The British Journal of Sociology*, 59 (1), 59-77.
- White, L. (1990). *The Comforts of Home: Prostitution in Colonial Nairobi*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
- Whyte, K. P. (2018). Indigenous science (fiction) for the Anthropocene: Ancestral dystopics and fantasies of climate change crises. *E Nature and Space*, 1 (1-2), 224-242.
- Zulu, B. (2015 May 27). Zimbabweans welcome ConCourt ruling on prostitution arrest. VOA <https://www.voazimbabwe.com/a/zimbabweans-welcome-concourt-ruling-on-prostitution>